

The molybdenum content of this solution was determined by using 8-hydroxyquinoline. It was diluted to give $M \times 10^{-3}$ molybdenum solution. The reagent solution, buffer solutions, instruments etc. were the same as described in Part I. (*loc. cit.*)

Nature of the Complex formed.—In a set of experiments, mixtures containing varying proportions of molybdenum: reagent were prepared and the optical densities at different wave-lengths in each case measured. In all the cases the maximum absorption occurred at $416 \text{ m}\mu$, thus indicating the formation of only one complex with the reagent (Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437).

Composition of the Complex

The molar composition of the molybdenum complex was investigated by the following methods.

Job's Method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113).—The molybdenum content in the final solution was varied between $4 \times 10^{-6} M$ and $28 \times 10^{-6} M$ and the final p_H was kept at about 3.2. Absorption was measured, after 30 minutes, at 415 and 425 $\text{m}\mu$. Fig. 1 shows the curves obtained by applying this method. The maxima at 0.75 indicate the ratio of molybdenum to reagent as 1:3.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Slope Ratio Method (Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488).—The concentration of the variable component was varied from $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $15 \times 10^{-5} M$ in presence of excess concentration of $8 \times 10^{-4} M$ of the constant component. The p_H of the solution was kept at about 3.2. Fig. 2 shows the measured optical density at 425 $\text{m}\mu$ plotted against the concentration of the variable component. The slopes of the two straight lines give molybdenum to reagent ratio as 1:3.

Molar Ratio Method (Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111).—

FIG. 3

A series of solutions was prepared at p_H 3.2 with a constant concentration of molybdenum at $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ and keeping the molybdenum to reagent ratio at 1:1 to 1:30. The curve 'a' in Fig. 3 does not show any sharp break owing to the dissociation of the complex in dilute solutions. By adding 5 c.c. of 1M-KCl solution to suppress the dissociation of the complex, a break is obtained (Fig. 3, curve 'b') at the ratio of 3 moles of the reagent to 1 mole of molybdenum. The break in the curve is not very sharp, indicating that the electrolyte concentration has not much influence in decreasing the dissociation of the complex in solution.

Conductivity Method.—The formula of the molybdenum complex could not be studied by applying conductivity method because of the slowness of the reaction. After each addition of the reagent solution to the molybdenum solution, it had to be kept for about 25 minutes for completion of the reaction, thus making the method unworkable. However, this observation has been made use of in studying the kinetics of the reaction.

Kinetics of the Reaction

The colour of the molybdenum complex is initially pale yellow, which gradually changes to orange-yellow. Since the intensity of colour is proportional to the extent of complex formation, it is concluded that the kinetics of the reaction can be studied spectrophotometrically by noting the changes in absorption with time.

FIG. 4

To study this problem 1 c.c. of $M \times 10^{-5}$ molybdenum solution was added to 40 c.c. of $M \times 10^{-5}$ reagent solution at p_H 3.2 and the volume made up to 50 c.c. The final concentration of molybdenum was thus $2 \times 10^{-5} M$. A stop-watch was started

at the time of mixing the solutions. The absorption of the reaction mixture was measured at definite intervals of time at 425 mμ. Fig. 4 records the change

of absorption with time. The absorption becomes constant after 23 minutes and has been observed to remain constant for 3 hours.

DISCUSSION

The dissociation of the complex in solution can be written as:

α being the degree of dissociation and C , the concentration of the complex, assuming no dissociation. The dissociation constant K is given by the equation

$$K = \frac{\alpha C \times (3\alpha C)^3}{C(1-\alpha)} = \frac{27\alpha^4 C^3}{1-\alpha}$$

From curve 'a', Fig. 3

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m} = \frac{29 - 9.5}{29} = 0.672$$

where the terms have their usual significance. The concentration C of the complex is equal to the total concentration of the molybdenum, which is $2 \times 10^{-5} M$. By substituting these values in the above equation, the value of K at 25° comes to 1.34×10^{-13} . Hence, the stability constant K' of the complex is equal to 7.44×10^{13} .

The standard free energy of formation of the complex from sodium molybdate and 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine is calculated from the relation $\Delta F^\circ = RT \ln K$ and works out to be -17.55 K cal./mole at 25° .

Molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , is equal to the slope of the straight line 'a' in Fig. 2, which is equal to 1.5×10^3 .

For studying the kinetics of the reaction between molybdenum and the reagent, the reaction may be written as:

Under experimental conditions where concentration of the reagent is sufficiently large in comparison to the concentration of molybdenum so that even when all molybdenum has been converted into the form of the complex there is practically no change in the concentration of the reagent, the reaction may satisfy the first order equation, thus behaving as a pseudo-unimolecular reaction.

The equation for a first order reaction may be written as:

$$t = \frac{2.303}{k} \cdot \log \frac{a}{a-x} = \frac{2.303}{k} \cdot \log a - \frac{2.303}{k} \cdot \log (a-x)$$

where k is the first order velocity constant, a is the initial concentration of molybdenum, x , the concentration of the complex at any instant. The initial concentration a of molybdenum is proportional to the maximum absorption E_m , shown by horizontal portion of the curve (Fig. 4). The concentration x of the complex at any instant is proportional to the measured absorption E_s at that instant. Hence, the concentration of unchanged molybdenum is proportional to $(E_m - E_s)$. Table I records these values at different intervals of time.

TABLE I

$$E_m(a) = 22.$$

Time.	$E_t(x)$.	$E_m - E_t(a-x)$.	$\text{Log}(E_m - E_t)$
1.7 mins.	14	8	0.9031
3.0	16	6	0.7781
5.5	18	4	0.6021
7.5	19	3	0.4771
10.0	20	2	0.3010
12.0	20.5	1.5	0.1761
14.0	21	1	0.0000

By plotting t against $\log(E_m - E_t)$, a straight line is obtained, showing that the reaction is of first order (Fig. 5). From the slope of this straight line, the value of k can be calculated by means of the above equation. On calculation the specific reaction rate comes to 0.1606.

FIG. 5

The authors express their gratitude to Principal Bhim Sen for providing facilities in the college and to Prof. K. P. Haldar for taking keen interest in the present work.

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Received June, 14, 1958